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THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN LEADERSHIP STYLES, EMPLOYEE SATISFACTION AND LOYALTY

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Abstract:

Job loyalty and satisfaction have received significant attention in the studies of work place. This is due to the general recognition that these variables can be the major determinants of organizational performance and effectiveness. This study examined the effects of leadership styles on job satisfaction and loyalty in car manufacturing industry in Iran. The leadership styles used in this study are consideration and initiating structure, transformational, and transactional. The results showed that traditional leadership styles in the Iranian automotive industry are used as dominant styles by managers and average level of employee satisfaction is low. The traditional leadership style has negative relationships with employee satisfaction. There is a negative relationship between leadership style and employee loyalty as well.

Keyword: Leadership styles, employee satisfaction, loyalty

Introduction:

A number of researchers have described that leadership the influence on individuals to fulfill their obligations and interest. Other groups have defined the leadership as the influence on subordinate to achieve the organizational goals with an emphasis on the relationships between individuals.

A well-known series of leadership studies that commenced at the University of Michigan in the 1950s, with the objective of identifying the principles and types of leadership styles led to greater productivity and enhanced job satisfaction among workers. The studies identified two broad leadership styles - an employee orientation and a production orientation. They also identified three critical characteristics of effective leaders - task-oriented behavior, relationship-oriented behavior and participative leadership. Transformational Leaders attended the current needs of subordinates and pay a high attention to their rewards for every action, mutual support and bilateral transactions.

Based on the theory of transformational leadership a leader requires the use of local actors to perform the duties required for an organization to achieve the desired goals. In this context, the goal of transformational leadership is to ensure that the path to achieve the goals is clearly perceived by local actors, resolve potential barriers within the system and encourages actors to achieve predetermined objectives. Another researcher, Bernard M. Bass (1985), extended the work of Burns (1978) by explaining the psychological mechanisms that underlie transforming and transactional leadership; Bass also used the term "transformational" instead of "transforming." Bass added to the initial concepts of Burns (1978) to help explain how transformational leadership could be measured, as well as how it impacts follower motivation and performance. The extent to which a leader is transformational, is measured first, in terms of his influence on the followers. The followers of such a leader feel trust, admiration, loyalty and respect for the leader and because of the qualities of the transformational leader are willing to work harder than originally expected. These outcomes occur because the transformational leader offers followers something more than just working for self gain; they provide followers with an inspiring mission and vision and give them an identity. The leader transforms and motivates followers through his or her idealized influence (earlier referred to as charisma), intellectual stimulation and individual consideration.

This article covers the followings: First, the types of leadership styles are introduced in the second part job satisfaction will be introduced. In the third part describe the employee loyalty. The last part will be considered for the research methodology, statistical, conclusions and recommendations.

Literature review:

Leadership styles:

Leadership contributes significantly in the success and failure of an organization (Lok and Crawford, 2004,). Leadership is the process of influencing employees with enthusiasm and the way that their maximum effort to achieve group goals. The manner, in which the leader uses his influence to achieve goals, is called leadership style. Leadership style takes care of endurance goals and requirements in different situations. Burns (1978) and other researchers (see Avolio, 1999a and b, 2002; Bass, 1996, 1997, 1998, 1999) contrasted transformational leaders to transactional leaders, who appeal to subordinates 'self-interest by establishing exchange relationships with them. This type of leadership involves managing in the more conventional sense of clarifying subordinate responsibilities, rewarding them for meeting objectives, and correcting them for failing to meet objectives. Although empirically separable, these two types of leadership-transformational and transactional-are both displayed by effective leaders. In addition to these two styles, these researchers distinguished a laissez-faire style that

is marked by a general failure to take responsibility for managing (Eagly, et al. 2003, Moezzi, et al. 2012, Jahanshahi, et al. 2011c).

Transformational leadership attributes, such as empowerment and clear vision, are often seen as important elements for employee job satisfaction and commitment (Sergiovanni and Corbally, 1984; Smith and Peterson, 1988). This type of leadership style is often associated with a flatter organizational structure and low power distance as in western firms (Chen, 2001). On the contrary, Asian firms tend to be more bureaucratic, hierarchical, have central decision making and are policy driven. Leadership tends to be based on position, authority and seniority (Lok and Crawford, 2004).

The results of research by Hessari (1997) showed arithmetically higher means were obtained with initiating structure leadership behavior than consideration leadership behavior for all participants. The most meaningful significance occurred when consideration leadership behavior was a predictor of satisfaction with supervision among all respondents pooled together. Consideration and initiating structure were shown to be significant predictors of satisfaction with job in general together among all respondents. The result of correlation matrices showed that consideration and initiating structure were positively and significantly correlated with each other and with satisfaction with supervision for all respondents whereas satisfaction level of employees was less than medium.

Job satisfaction:

Job satisfaction includes a level of positive feelings and views that people hold toward their jobs. When a person claims to be highly satisfied with a job this means that he/she really likes a job, and has good feelings about their job and values that job highly. The findings of the research show that employees with higher job satisfaction are in ideal condition regarding their physical and mental being. People's job satisfaction is divided into two kinds of internal and external satisfaction. Regarding external satisfaction, employees show their satisfaction from factors such as payment, promotion, employer's encouragement and interaction with colleagues (originates from responsibilities). And in internal satisfaction, employees show their satisfaction from feeling of responsibility, social status and position, situation, independence and self esteem based on tasks and works. A person's assessment of his/her work and satisfaction or lack of satisfaction from that job is a general result from various pillars which make up his/her job (Robbins, 1995, Sadeghi et al. 2013, Hashemzadeh et al. 2011 & Nawaser et al., 2011, Jahanshahi, et al. 2010).

Job satisfaction includes a level of positive feelings and views that people hold toward their jobs. When a person claims to be highly satisfied with a job this means that he/she really likes a job, and has good feelings about their job and values that job highly. Job satisfaction literature reveals connections between job satisfaction and various other influencing factors (Hardman, 1996, Jahanshahi, et al. 2011a).

Job loyalty:

Becker (1960) described loyalty as a process, he believes that if someone with a better knowledge of the conditions of a job, higher salaries and better conditions, refuses to accept the job in order to keep his current job, he is considered as loyal individual to the organization. In view of Allen and Meyer (1997) Loyalty is identified by three factors:

- 1 - Strong belief in the value of the organization.
- 2 - Great efforts to achieve organizational goals
- 3 - High desire to stay in the organization.

In this model, an individual's loyalty to the organization is because of the commitment that the individual have to the organization and its overall objectives (Savarykyn 2009, Jahanshahi, et al. 2011b). In the study of Amiran (2005), loyalty, sense of emotional and spiritual belonging to the organization and the sensitivity of what clearly manifests the organization have been considered. Rachel (2009) employee loyalty is attributed to continued cooperation with the organization.

In this study indexes are considered for employee's loyalty which includes 1. Desire to continue working with organization 2. Accomplishing more work 3. Sense of belonging to the organization 4. Take on more responsibility. Loyalty of employees with the company, a sense of belonging to the organization and tendency to work towards achieving the goals of the organization has been considered in this research.

Research framework:

Figure 1: conceptual model of study

Hypotheses:

First Major hypothesis: There is a significant positive relationship between leadership styles and job satisfaction.

Minor Hypothesis:

1. There is a significant positive relationship between leadership traditional style (Consideration) and employee job satisfaction.
2. There is a significant positive relationship between leadership traditional style (Initiating Structure) and employee job satisfaction.
3. There is a significant positive relationship between transformational leadership style and employee job satisfaction.

4. There is a significant positive relationship between transactional leadership style and employee job satisfaction.

Second main hypothesis: There is a significant positive relationship between manager's leadership styles and employee job loyalty.

Minor hypotheses:

1. There is a significant positive relationship between traditional leadership styles (Consideration) and the employees' level of loyalty

2. There is a significant positive relationship between traditional leadership styles (Initiating Structure) and the employees' level of loyalty

3. There is a significant positive relationship between transformational leadership styles and the employees' level of loyalty

4. There is a significant and positive relationship between transactional leadership style and the employees' level of loyalty

Methodology:

The method of data collection was questionnaire. Afterwards, the content reliability method was used to ensure the reliability of the questionnaire. Therefore, the researcher makes use of some academic experienced professors who had long experiences in research and specialized in management to design the questionnaire. Considering their corrective comments, the questionnaire had the necessary credibility. Leadership styles, employee loyalty and job satisfaction questionnaires were used as research tools using a four point likert scale (with 4 = completely agree, to 1 = completely disagree). Leadership styles as independent variables and job satisfaction and employee loyalty were considered as the dependent variables. Descriptive statistics and inferential statistics were used in this study. The description and analysis of research was performed using Pearson methods and the research is of descriptive and correlative type. Descriptive statistics are numbers that are used to summarize and describe data. The branch of statistics concerned with drawing conclusions about a population from a sample. Questionnaires were distributed in such a way that the Multi-factor Leadership Questionnaires were distributed among employees at different levels. Then the satisfaction and job loyalty questionnaire was distributed among the employees of the organization and information was collected based on the collected questionnaires. Reliability is the consistency of measurement, or the degree to which an instrument measures the same way each time it is used under the same condition with the same subjects. For determining reliability of the study Cronbach's Alpha method was used. Cronbach's alpha of 898% for leadership style, 898% for employee loyalty and 767% for employee satisfaction was calculated respectively. Since the alpha coefficient of greater than 70% is acceptable, it can be concluded that the questionnaires high reliability. This study was conducted in mid 2011 till late 2012.

Data analysis:

All statistical analyses were carried out using the SPSS statistical computer package, Version 12. Responses to the items measuring, leadership styles, job satisfaction and loyalty, were factor analyzed, and factor scores obtained were used for subsequent data analysis. In this section for better understanding of the population first the demographic characteristic of manufacturing lines staff in Saipa and Iran-Khoro automobile Industry.

Descriptive information of sample by age and sex

Age	Number	Percent	Gender	Number	Percent
30 and below	47	15.4	Man	292	95.7
31-40	163	53.4	Woman	13	0.043
40 and above	75	24.6	Total	305	100
No Response	20	0.07			
Total	305	100			

Result of study:

Identification of the dominant style of leadership in the Iranian automotive industry with respect to employees' satisfaction and loyalty

Table 1: Identification of the dominant style of leadership

Index	Employee satisfaction	Employee Loyalty	Leadership Style
Mean	2/9	2/98	3/36
Dominant style	Traditional Leadership Styles (Consideration)	Traditional Leadership Styles (Initiating Structure)	Traditional Leadership Styles 1, 2

Kolmogorov-Smirnov test used to determine the normality of the data and the findings are presented in Table 2. The results of this test illustrate the normal distribution of all variables in the population at a significance level of $\alpha / 0 = 05$. It is noteworthy to state that in the case of normal distribution of data, the correlation coefficient for correlation can be used.

Dimension	Initiating Structure	Consideration	Transformational	Transactional	Job Satisfaction	Job Loyalty
Mean	86.16	75.73	48.9	35.8	29.1	27.5
Standard deviation	24.5	24.1	18.7	16.4	11.8	10.6
Kolmogorov-Smirnov	0.727	0.756	0.818	0.678	0.786	0.885
Significance level	0.665	0.634	0.705	0.906	0.874	0.754

The results showed that traditional leadership styles as the dominant styles used in the automotive industry are applied by managers have an average level of employee satisfaction is lower than the average. The below table shows that:

- There is a weak positive correlation between Transformational & Job Satisfaction scores ($r / 0 = 28$) and ($P < 0/05$), which states that an increase in Transformational score leads to a greater job satisfaction.

- Transformational & Job Loyalty score correlated positively ($r / 0 = 457$) and ($P < 0/05$), which states that an increase in Transformational scores cause more job loyalty.

Determining the correlation of variables using Pearson's correlation coefficient

Variables	Correlation Type	Correlation Level	Correlation Direction	Significance level
Transformational & Job Satisfaction	Pearson	28%	Weak and Positive	0/05
Transformational & Job Loyalty	Pearson	457%	Positive	0/05
Transactional & Job Satisfaction	Pearson	-276%	Weak and Positive	0/01
Transactional & Job Loyalty	Pearson	18%	Weak and Positive	0/01
Initiating Structure & Job Satisfaction	Pearson	-17%	Negative	0/05
Initiating Structure & Job Loyalty	Pearson	-293%	Negative	0/05
Consideration & Job Satisfaction	Pearson	-365%	Negative	0/05
Consideration & Job Loyalty	Pearson	409%	Positive	0/05

*Significant correlation at the level 0.05

- Transactional & Job Satisfaction scores possess a weak negative correlation ($r / 0 = -276$) and ($P < 0/01$), which states that an increase in Transactional score would lead to lesser Satisfaction.
- Transactional & Job Loyalty scores have a weak positive relationship ($r / 0 = 18$), and ($P < 0/01$), which states that an increase in Transactional score leads to greater job loyalty.
- Initiating Structure & Job Satisfaction score correlated negatively ($r / 0 = -17$) and ($P < 0/05$) which states that an increase in Initiating Structure scores results in lower job satisfaction.
- Initiating Structure & Job Loyalty scores and weak negative relationship ($r / 0 = -293$) and ($P < 0/05$) which states that an increase in Initiating Structure scores result in lower job loyalty.
- Consideration & Job Satisfaction score correlated negatively ($r / 0 = -365$) and ($P < 0/05$), which states that an increase in the Consideration causes lower job satisfaction.
- Consideration & Job Loyalty score correlated positively ($r / 0 = 409$) and ($P < 0/05$), which states that an increase in the Consideration will cause more job loyalty.

Discussion and conclusion:

Job satisfaction is one of the most important factors in satisfaction of life and all human relationships and behaviors to directly or indirectly influenced by how his/her employment. So it is better to help people to find a suitable job. Be prepared to play a role in their job satisfactorily.

To conclude, this study is an active attempt to investigate the effects of leadership style on job satisfaction and loyalty, and how this might be applied among car manufacturing managers. Although many of the

findings in this study are left unexplained, it has suggested some interesting topics for future cross cultural research. The study confirms that leadership styles are important organizational antecedents of job satisfaction and loyalty in Asian automobile industries.

In the final section we mention some points we have encountered with the research process and can be a field for future research by other researchers:

- The survival of the Organization is supported by the customers. Therefore, it is suggested to the researchers to study the relationship between service and the behavior of customers such as customer satisfaction and loyalty.
- It is recommended to researchers looking for the answer to the next question, which is between the desire to serve up and job satisfaction on the other people in the car industry and related industries, there is a significant relationship.
- It is recommended to researchers looking for to find answer to question such as whether there is a significant relationship between the tendency towards service and job satisfaction in the car industry and related industries.

Limitation of study:

The findings of this study should be cautiously taken into account due to the following detailed reasons:

Sample size limitations: low population sample is one of the limitations of this study. This limitation is due to the concerns of the employees ' career and the limitation of the scope of the research to specific geographic areas and the project time limitations.

Time limit: due to shortage of time (7 months) to plan, prepare and perform it.

Geographic restrictions: Due to the unique nature of the population sample is one organization only.

Tool limitations: all three questionnaires used in the study are considered as those which are dependent to culture. And one of the problems that have plagued the Islamic research works is that they think the real answer may have bad consequences for them and take the treacherous protector method and answers those questions which are popular in the society.

Limitations of the test sample: group sex, most of the community has been selected among the men.

Gender limitations: most of the male population was selected.

Sample restriction: it cannot certainly be argued that the employees who responded to the questionnaires were selected at random from the employees of this organization, because only a small number of units were considered for the study.

Limitation of facilities: hard and non-flexible provisions of some of the Universities' library giving books to students to other institutions, absence of researcher or lack of access to reference sources listed on domestic and foreign books and waste of time in examining and addressing some of the issues, concepts, and recent research.

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